

DIGITAL INSIDE DENSITY PROFILE ACQUISITION METHOD OF CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITE BY A COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY

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1 Introduction

Carbon/carbon composite has many inside voids and mechanical and thermal properties can be diminished by the inside voids. This paper describes the inside digital density profile evaluation study of the carbon/carbon materials for a missile propulsion system. The standard density specimens which consisted of known density materials are designed and manufactured. The universal curve for density to amplitude of the standard density specimens can be acquired by a computed tomography. After using this universal curve, the inside density profile of the carbon/carbon material can be plotted. To verify this result, we measured the densities of each position in the carbon/carbon by water immersion method and studied morphology of the carbon/carbon material. We can conclude that the density profile evaluation method by a computed tomography can be used for quality assurance method.[1-2]

2 Experimental

2.1 Computed Tomography

Fig.1 shows a computed tomography flow diagram and Fig.2 shows a figure of computed tomography in this experiment. It contains X-ray beam generator, detector, scanning unit, graphic display system. The collimator is located at X-ray beam generator and detector to prevent beam scattering and fan type X-ray beam. The X-ray beam from generator is detected at detector using 32 channel cadmium tungsten scintillator after penetrating specimen and collimator. [3-4]

Fig.1. Flow diagram of a computed tomography

Fig.2. Figure of a computed tomography

2.2 Standard density materials

Fig.3 shows a schematic diagram of standard density materials and they are made by graphite with different density.

Fig.3. Schematic diagram of standard density material

3 Results

3.1 Correction of linear beam hardening

Computed tomography image is affected by linear beam hardening and Fig.4 shows a corrected image by polychromatic correction method.

Fig.4. Correction of beam hardening

3.2 Density distributions by voxel size

The voxel size from computed tomography is shown in Fig. 5. If a void is existed in a voxel by the computed tomography image the calculated density will be decreased and the density distribution will be broad. The density of standard density materials is related to CT number and table 1 shows normal distribution of standard density materials A, B, C, D and table 2 shows confidence level for each voxel size.

Fig.4. Schematic diagram of voxel image

Fig.5. Standard deviation according to voxel size

Table 1 CT number of the standard density materials

Standard density materials	CT number				
	Min	Max	Mean	RMSD	Percent
A	17,669	18,795	18,247.59	184.73	1.012
B	17,809	19,048	18,370.69	185.60	1.010
C	18,331	19,679	19,045.14	193.47	1.016
D	18,901	20,224	19,548.53	216.90	1.110

Table 2 Confidence level for each voxel size

Voxel size	Min	Max	Mean	RMSD	Confidence
0.2×0.2×1.5 mm	18901.00	20224.00	19548.53	216.91	42.00%
1.0×1.0×1.5 mm	19269.30	19794.80	19548.53	101.35	76.37%
2.0×2.0×1.5 mm	19448.91	19666.84	19548.53	49.18	98.53%

3.3 CT number profiles of carbon/carbon composite

Fig. 6 and Fig. 7 shows CT number profile of carbon/carbon composite from computed tomography.

Fig.6. CT number of X axis

Fig.7. CT number of Y axis

3.4 Density distributions of carbon/carbon

The results of digital inside density profile acquisition program shows Fig.8-9.

Fig.8. Procedure of digital inside density profile acquisition program

Fig.9. Result of digital inside density profile acquisition program

3.5 Morphology of carbon/carbon

Fig. 10 shows carbon/carbon composite inside morphology.

Fig.10. Morphology of carbon/carbon composite

4 Conclusions

The standard density materials are designed and the CT number of 2.0 x 2.0 x 1.5mm voxel size by the computed tomography is converted to the density value in the carbon/carbon material. The converted density value is compared to real density by water immersion method. Two density values are very similar at same position in the carbon/carbon material.

References

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